

Marketing Strategies in the Development of the Halal Products and Services Industry

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ABSTRACT

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A marketing strategy is a plan that helps a business sell and promote a product or service. The modern world is so diverse and rapidly changing that companies need to constantly adapt to the environment and create conditions for product promotion. Halal products are not new to European countries, but many consumers treat them as exotic, yet they are still interested in consuming them. The combination of approaches to developing marketing strategies and studying the specifics of halal product promotion is the basis of the research topic. Accordingly, the goal is to assess the current state of distribution of halal products in Europe and the world as a whole, as well as to develop recommendations for the application of marketing strategies for halal producers. The study found that in the future, the volume of production and sales of halal products will increase, and producers need to adapt their marketing strategies to market conditions. It is the recommendations on the adaptation of the main marketing strategies for halal producers that were developed in the course of the study.

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Introduction

A marketing strategy is a comprehensive plan of action to promote a product and increase the company's profit (Grewal et al., 2020). A marketing strategy is necessary for companies when entering markets, launching a new product, expanding the sales market, and other major changes. If a company has plans to take a leading position in the industry, develop new directions, increase production volumes, and conquer the global market, a strategy will help systematise the steps to achieve its goals.

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Increasing competitiveness is an important aspect of marketing strategy. It involves identifying and disclosing the company's competitive advantages: through the introduction of new technologies, development and launch of new products, improvement of service quality, rebranding, etc.

A carefully thought-out strategy helps to allocate the company's resources and increase sales. In some situations, an increase in profits is possible by increasing production, while in other cases it is necessary to abandon unpromising products and focus on the most successful ones. Sometimes, it is important to put all your efforts into promotion. The strategy defines what needs to be done to strengthen current positions and gain new market shares (Bamel & Bamel, 2021). Without it, efforts will bring little effect: you will have to test many hypotheses and spend your budget. With a strategy, a company better understands where to move and what to focus on. Resources - both financial and labour - are spent rationally.

If the current strategy is ineffective, it should be revised, or a new marketing strategy should be developed. It is also necessary to do this in the event of major changes within the firm or the market. There are several stages to developing a marketing strategy. At the first stage, the company analyses the market, competitors, and its own business processes, at the second stage it determines its immediate actions and implements changes, and at the third stage it examines the effectiveness of the implemented measures and updates the strategy in the light of the market situation.

Of course, the strategy should consider the specifics of the goods that the company produces, and if the company enters the market with specific products, such as those that meet halal standards, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of the audience and the possibility of expanding markets.

In view of this, the purpose of the article is to assess the current state of the distribution of halal products in Europe and the world in general and to develop recommendations for the application of marketing strategies for halal producers.

Literature review

The modern world is characterised by a huge variety of tastes, preferences, religious beliefs, and cultural characteristics, which, in turn, contributes to the diversity of goods and services that will satisfy the most demanding needs of different consumer groups. To ensure growth in sales of products and services, companies are increasingly using integrated marketing tools rather than isolated ones and are developing a comprehensive marketing strategy that can form a systematic approach to the marketing activities of each company, depending on the conditions and specifics of the market.

Based on a literature review (Andersson et al., 2022; Arora & Sanni, 2019; Dilovar, 2022; Metaxas et al., 2021; Vyshnivska, 2021), we can generalise that the essence of a marketing strategy is that it systemises and helps to evaluate a company's resources to redistribute them to more efficient channels. Promotion channels can include outdoor advertising, partnerships with bloggers, advertising on social media, radio, television, and search engines.

A company needs marketing strategy tools to achieve its goals: to increase market share, occupy a niche, or meet a revenue target (Marini et al., 2021; Dey et al., 2020). Such tools can include pricing, communication with the target audience, and brand positioning. Larger sections

of marketing can also be considered tools, such as SEO, content marketing, email marketing, SMM (Morra et al., 2018; Woloszko, 2020).

In the classical marketing theory, Michael Porter was the first researcher to propose the formation of a marketing strategy. He proposed the main strategies based on the current positioning of the company and focused on its further active development - Table 1.

Table 1.

Basic marketing strategies according to Michael Porter with a description of their application in the modern world

Porter's strategy	Peculiarities of strategy implementation in the modern world	Examples of companies applying the strategy
Cost leadership	The company optimises processes and cuts costs. This allows it to reduce the price of the product and thus attract a large audience.	Typically, this strategy can be applied to large manufacturing and trading enterprises, supermarket chains, such as Costco, IKEA
Differentiation	The company offers products or services that are different from those of its competitors and emphasises this difference. This can be differentiation by product, service, or image	It is used by companies that produce goods that can be significantly differentiated or provide services where it is easy to achieve a customer-centric approach. For example, IKEA, Nike, Apple
Focusing	The company shifts its focus from a product to a specific market segment. For example, stores selling vinyl records or goods for preschoolers	The strategy can be applied in companies with a large range of small products that need to be adapted to different markets. For example, Lidl, L'Oréal

Compiled by the author based on (Al-Sai et al., 2022; Ardito et al., 2021; Bannikov et al., 2022; Dash et al., 2021; Gabellini & Scaramuzzi, 2022; Lucato et al., 2019; Rahardja, 2022)

It is also worth noting that it is possible to develop a related advertising strategy from two positioning. For example, IKEA follows the strategies of differentiation and cost leadership (Feshina et al., 2019). Customers were offered furniture that they could assemble themselves, and by optimising production processes, the company reduced prices for its goods, resulting in a double benefit of increased sales and reduced furniture assembly costs.

However, companies should not spread out their marketing strategies too thinly, as combining three development strategies at once can lead to significant cost increases in the short term and even bankruptcy. Developing a product that has significant features requires investment. If you reduce the price and keep the focus on a highly specialised niche with an initially small target audience, the investment may not pay off.

The specifics of marketing strategies also depend on the company's internal financial situation and market position. Another marketing classic, Philip Kotler, identifies four competitive strategies - Table 2.

Table 2.

Basic marketing strategies according to Philip Kotler with a description of their application in the modern world

Strategy	Characteristics	Features of application in the modern world
Extensions	The company's market share increases through investment. This strategy reduces current revenues as the company scales up production: it builds new plants, hires staff, and purchases equipment	The strategy should be applied with caution in the volatile stock market of 2021- 2022
Retention	The company maintains its current market position by focusing on promoting goods or services that generate the main income, despite low growth rates	It can be considered one of the best strategies for a period of crisis or unstable external environment. Allows you to wait out the "hard times"
Harvesting	The strategy of maximising profits here and now is suitable for goods and services with an uncertain future. The company relies on quick revenue from their sale and, accordingly, a rapid reduction in costs before sales decline	It is optimal to apply to certain areas or directions of the company's activities without simultaneously transferring the entire company to such a strategy
Disinvestment	Closing one line of business and reallocating resources to a new industry or new product development.	This marketing strategy can be used in the event of a business liquidation or, for example, if the costs of producing a certain product reduce the company's profit. In general, it is best used for companies at the maturity stage that require a significant reorganisation

Compiled by the author on the basis of (Arslanalp et al., 2019; Barbaglia et al., 2022; Dykan et al., 2021; Girard, 2019; Martin et al., 2022; Shahid & Qureshi, 2022)

It is logical to decide to implement a particular strategy when a thorough analysis of the company's external and internal environment has been carried out and it has been established that all the prerequisites for developing and implementing a particular strategy are in place.

The most common and used tools for strategic marketing analysis may be the following (Kilani, 2021; Steinhoff & Palmatier, 2021; Timoumi et al., 2022):

SWOT analysis is an overview of the company's strengths and weaknesses, as well as opportunities and threats in the environment. It helps to determine the current position of the company and the key factors that influence the goals of the strategy and further decisions (Holwerda et al., 2021).

PEST-analysis of the company's external environment, which allows to identify political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors. It helps to understand macroeconomic and socio-cultural trends affecting the business (Martin et al., 2022). Competitor analysis - shows what the competitive environment is like, what advantages and disadvantages are typical for competing companies. It provides valuable data on the possibilities of using the tools used by competitors (Poltinina et al., 2020).

Market segmentation. It allows you to divide the market into groups of similar consumers, better understand the target audience, and adapt advertising campaigns to these segments (Kumar, 2020).

Positioning. It helps to determine how a company communicates the values and benefits of a product or service to customers, create a unique selling proposition and brand strategy (Olson et al., 2021).

Targeted market segment management. It shows which customers bring in the most profit, so the company can focus on the needs of this audience and attract new customers of this profile.

BCG Matrix. It is used to analyse a company's product portfolio and determine which ones require more attention and which ones should be diversified.

Ansoff Matrix. Describes possible growth strategies for the company and helps to determine the strategy for positioning the product in the market.

Targeted management of the marketing mix. It allows you to adapt the product, price, promotion, and other elements of the marketing mix to market segments and customer needs.

After applying a set of strategic analytical tools, the company will have sufficient prerequisites for developing and further implementing a marketing strategy.

Companies that market halal products and related services are no exception and need to properly plan their labelling activities and develop and implement marketing strategies.

However, it is worth understanding the specifics and features of products labelled halal. Today, halal-labelled products are increasingly common in supermarkets, chain and farm shops, marketplaces, markets, and fairs. And this is typical for countries where the Muslim population is not predominant, but the concept of halal products originates from Muslim culture.

For Muslims, the term "halal" means that a product complies with Islamic traditions (Olson et al., 2021). In other words, it confirms that the product does not contain components that are prohibited for Muslims to consume, such as pork or blood. Not every product can be labelled halal. There is a system of voluntary certification of products and services for compliance with Islamic requirements - the International Halal System. In each Muslim country, special structures have been established to control and verify the raw materials and technological processes of production for compliance with halal standards and to ensure the proper use of halal labelling.

Obviously, such food is not harmful to humans. For example, vegetables do not contain nitrates, sausage does not contain carcinogens and gmos, yoghurts do not contain artificial colours, etc. Confectionery products with such labelling cannot contain alcohol, whey and protein, gelatin, carmine, glycerin, as well as mono- and diglycerides of fatty acids, esters and glycerides of acids, sucrose esters, polyglycerol.

That is why halal products are bought all over the world not only by Muslims but also by people of other faiths who care about healthy eating for themselves and their families. For example, in the United Kingdom, home to 2 million Muslims, halal products are sold annually to 6 million people (Olson et al., 2021). In countries with a large Muslim population, such as France, more than 60% of all meat products are labelled halal. This allows producers not to miss out on the mass consumer segment. In addition, research shows that the mass consumer has a positive attitude towards halal products. Thus, today in non-Muslim countries, halal products have become a kind of quality mark that indicates that goods meet certain requirements.

Therefore, for halal producers, choosing a marketing strategy is as necessary as for other companies, as the market requires conscious promotion of products and consideration of its demands and needs.

Method

The study is focused on analysing the consumption of halal products in Europe and the world with the subsequent development of recommendations for the creation and implementation of marketing strategies for halal producers. To achieve this goal, the method of statistical data analysis will be used to identify the dynamics of consumption of halal products in European countries and to diagnose the structure of consumption of these products in Europe and the Muslim world. Further, the method of generalisation and systematisation was used to study different approaches to the development and implementation of marketing strategies. The method of adaptation was used to study the experience of well-known global companies and to adapt their experience to identify the main opportunities for using marketing strategies in the production and promotion of halal goods and services.

Data analysis and results

The global halal food and beverage market is segmented by product type (halal food, halal beverages, and halal supplements), with distribution channels mainly represented through hypermarkets/supermarkets, speciality stores, convenience stores, and other distribution channels. The main countries where halal products are most represented are the UK, Germany, France, Italy, Spain, Russia, and the rest of Europe.

The size of the halal market in Europe in 2022 is USD 13.75 billion, and by 2028 it will grow to USD 19.26 billion (Öztürk, 2022).

The preparation and consumption of halal food has a significant impact on members of the Islamic community. The global halal food and beverage market is expected to grow significantly due to the increasing Muslim population in the European region and growing concerns over food hygiene and safety. Consequently, producers are trying to change the entire value chain, from raw materials and product development to packaging, marketing, and spreading the word about the benefits of consuming these products through social media advertising. In the short term, halal food is gaining popularity among Muslim and non-Muslim consumers as it has matured from a religious sign to ensure food and beverage safety and hygiene. As a result, manufacturers and retailers are responding to this demand by producing halal products locally or importing them from other countries. Large European supermarket chains such as Tesco, ASDA, Auchan, Carrefour, and Edeka also offer halal meat departments in some stores (Öztürk, 2022). The growing European halal market has led manufacturers to expand their businesses into niche sectors, including bread, biscuits, cookies, and spreads. As such, the growing Muslim population in this region is projected to drive the market under study over the forecast period. Statistics on the supply of halal products are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1.

Statistics on the supply of halal products by country

Compiled by the author based on Öztürk (2022)

Fig. 1 shows the share of the halal market in different European countries compared to the share of the Muslim population. Particular attention should be paid to France, which has the largest Muslim population in Europe. Halal offerings have also taken Islamic law to a new level with a significant presence in the French food industry, supermarkets, and even restaurants. For example, according to a study conducted by the French Public Institute (Öztürk, 2022) in 2020, 59% of the Muslim population regularly consumes halal-certified meat, and 20% consume halal meat as much as possible. As the demand for halal food is constantly evolving, supermarkets have expanded their services and allocated more shelves for this type of product.

It is clear that Europe is only beginning to consume halal products, while the Muslim world has long been consuming such products. The top 10 countries in terms of consumption of halal goods and services are shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

Top 10 countries in terms of consumption of halal goods and services

Type of halal products	TOP-10 consumer countries	Type of halal products	TOP-10 consumer countries
Halal food	1. 1.	Halal media and entertainment	1. 1.
	2. 2.		2. 2.
	3. 3.		3. 3.
	4. 4.		4. 4.
	5. 5.		5. 5.
	6. 6.		6. 6.
	7. 7.		7. 7.
	8. 8. Saudi Arabia		8. 8.
	9. 9.		9. 9.
	10. 10.		10. Australia
Halal tourism	1. 1.	Halal medicines and cosmetics	1. 1.
	2. Malaysia.		2. Malaysia.
	3. 3.		3. 3.
	4. 4. Singapore		4. 4.
	5. 5.		5. Pakistan
	6. 6.		6. 6.
	7. 7.		7. 7. Saudi Arabia
	8. 8.		8. 8.
	9. 9.		9. 9.
	10. Saudi Arabia		10. Brunei

Compiled by the author on the basis of Öztürk (2022)

Since it is proved that halal products and services are not specific or new for most countries in Europe and the world today, the need to develop recommendations on the development and application of marketing strategies for producers of halal products and services is confirmed. At the same time, it should be emphasised that companies producing and selling halal products should not only focus on product promotion but also on information work to interest non-Muslim consumers in purchasing halal products and consuming halal services as those of high quality and capable of

Therefore, halal producers should study the experience of successful companies in terms of what marketing strategies they use and adopt their experience and adapt it to the specifics of the products and services they market. Possible areas of such adaptation are shown in Table 4.

Table 4.

Potential opportunities to use the experience of implementing marketing strategies to promote halal products

A company whose experience can be used	The essence of marketing strategy	Adapting a strategy to promote halal products and services
Nike	Retention strategy. To keep users' attention, the brand distributes motivational content and information that indicates the convenience and practicality of its products. From the very beginning of the brand's formation, the founder worked to promote activity and offer products that would make sports more convenient and enjoyable. Nike does not use content to directly advertise its products. Rather, it associates its clothing and footwear with sporting achievements and personal victories. This kind of information works well on the subconscious mind and encourages the target audience to new achievements. And thus, to new purchases of equipment.	The practice of constantly attracting attention to halal products from consumers in the form of advertisements in supermarkets, promoting the idea of eating halal products through social networks can be used
Bounty	Focusing strategy. Marketers of the Bounty paper towel brand decided to abstract from standard advertising media and focus on situations that are understandable to the buyer. Thus, giant spilled cups of coffee and huge melting ice cream appeared on the streets. And a modest city light with a roll of towels next to it - simple and straightforward. The campaign is based on guerrilla marketing, which is hard to ignore. The company continues to produce only paper products and is expanding its product range.	The focus strategy should include the possibility of focusing on the production of a certain type of halal product and expanding the line of halal products (e.g., yoghurts with new flavours, in bottles and glasses of different sizes, with different fat content, etc.)
Spotify	Expansion strategy. The music streaming service Spotify has relied on the convenience and practicality of its interface. Its attractive and practical design, a variety of features, and the availability of a free version of the service have helped it become a favourite among users, with nearly 300 million worldwide. Of this, half of music lovers use paid subscription services. Spotify's strategy is based on convenience and comfort for the user. For this purpose, the app even has artificial intelligence that selects new songs for the audio collection based on the listener's preferences.	The expansion strategy can be applied when you get consumers interested in new products and services by constantly piquing their curiosity

Gopro	Harvesting strategy. Extreme sports camera manufacturer gopro uses fan content in its social media posts. This helps to popularise the brand and attract new customers interested in high-quality action video. The manufacturer offers its own video editor, which automatically overlays a watermark with the brand logo on the video during editing. In this way, users not only share stories about their own adventures but also share the secret of unusual shooting. In addition, gopro regularly holds contests among its users, encouraging them to create original content with updated equipment and other valuable prizes.	The harvesting strategy can be applied by already successful companies by involving their regular customers in product advertising, which will make marketing tools for product promotion more adaptive to the audience
Sephora	Retention strategy Sephora has chosen to retain customers through a lucrative affiliate programme. The tier system used to differentiate customers gives the brand an element of exclusivity. About 80% of sales are made by current members of the loyalty programme, making the business as stable as possible. Market research has shown that 80% of customers use a smartphone to select or order products. That is why the brand's stores offer free Wi-Fi and a branded app with an attractive and intuitive interface.	The experience can be adapted as an opportunity to create a mobile application that will allow you to quickly check whether brands are halal.

Source: author's own development

However, when adapting the experience of leading companies, it is necessary to take into account mistakes that can negatively affect the results of strategy development and implementation:

- *Lack of clear goals.* Vague goals give a blurred focus, which makes it difficult to understand where the company is heading and whether it is achieving the desired results. It is necessary to clearly set financial targets and monitor their achievement.
- *Inadequate market and competitor analysis.* A lack of understanding of market conditions and the competitive environment leads to ineffective strategic decisions. SWOT and PEST analyses and competitor research are needed to assess the current state of the company and select the most appropriate strategy. In addition, it will make it possible to consider the specifics of tactical measures to implement the strategy.
- *Insufficient audience segmentation.* Targeting a broad market without clear segmentation risks wasting resources. Any business marketing strategy should take into account the needs and characteristics of specific audience segments. Sometimes it is advisable to use different marketing strategies for different market segments.
- *Ignoring market changes.* Ignoring new consumer preferences, technologies, and competition, companies are on the verge of losing competitiveness. Therefore, the creation and implementation of a strategy should be preceded by an analysis of new technologies and tools that can respond to market and audience demands.
- *No unique offer.* A company with a vague or indistinguishable offer from its competitors is less attractive to customers. Uniqueness and the ability to stand out are important in the market. Manufacturers of halal products need to show how their products are better than those that are not labelled halal and how they can positively affect the consumer who buys them (better quality, less harmful to health, moral satisfaction).
- *There is no system for monitoring and evaluating success indicators.* If it is unsuccessful, it will be unclear what and how to correct it. This is one of the key points.

To avoid making these most common mistakes, halal producers should focus on the following key tools for implementing marketing strategies.

SEO (Search Engine Optimisation) is the optimisation of a website for search engines such as Google. A well-thought-out SEO strategy can help a website rank high in search results, which will lead to increased traffic to the site and increased sales. To use SEO for business development, you must first research the keywords that potential customers use when searching for the goods or services offered by the company. Then optimise your website by using these keywords in your titles, meta descriptions, texts, and urls. It is also important to update your website regularly to keep it relevant and interesting for visitors. It is worth adding interesting information about halal products, encouraging visitors to visit the site to be able to collect personal data from customers (with their permission).

Email marketing, which remains quite popular today, is sending emails to potential and existing customers. It is one of the most effective ways to increase sales, as you can send targeted messages to your audience to encourage participation in promotions, sweepstakes, contests, and competitions. However, you need to comply with data protection and digital ethics requirements. You should create a list of subscribers by collecting the email addresses of customers and website visitors. Then develop a well-thought-out email template that is informative, attractive, and easy to read. Don't forget to include links to the website and offers for products or services that are offered or that need to be sold.

Another tool is sponsorship, which is a partnership between a business and another company or organisation to promote a brand. Sponsorships can help you reach new audiences, increase brand awareness, and boost sales. It's worth researching companies or organisations that might be interested in partnering with your business. Then develop a sponsorship plan that will be beneficial to both parties. For example, you can offer financial support for events held by another company or offer your products or services as prizes for contests or promotions.

PR events can also be used as a part of a marketing strategy, as it is the organisation of events that help draw attention to a brand and increase its awareness. It can be any event - from charity events to corporate parties. The concept of the event should be well thought out and reflect the brand in the best possible way, attracting the attention of the target audience.

Conclusion

The study found that a marketing strategy is a planned plan of activities used to promote goods and services. The main channels of promotion may include outdoor advertising, affiliate programmes, integration into blogging and social networks, search engine results, radio, and television. Marketing strategy tools allow you to increase your company's presence in the market, take a leading position in a certain area, and fulfil your earnings plan. These tools include pricing, customer communication and brand positioning, SEO, content marketing, and SMM. However, it has been proven that a marketing strategy will be effective only if the action plan for its implementation is as well-grounded as possible. A well-developed marketing strategy plan will help you to scale results effectively, avoid mistakes, systemise company resources, and allocate them correctly. The specifics of applying marketing strategies were considered in the context of promoting halal goods and services, which today occupy an increasing market share and are becoming increasingly popular in Europe and the world, as evidenced by statistical materials.

The paper also suggests adapting common marketing strategies of well-known companies for halal producers, which will improve public awareness of the essence of halal products and increase sales.

The study proposes to use the personal data of consumers with their consent, but the ethical aspect of using such data may become the basis for further research.

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